

ANALYSIS OF DEIXIS IN TRANSLATION OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK WORDS

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Annotatsiya: Deyxis - bu til va kontekst o'rtasidagi munosabatni aks ettiruvchi fundamental lingvistik hodisa. Tarjimashunoslikda deyxis hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi, chunki deyktik iboralar so'zlovchi, vaqt, joy va nutq vaziyatiga juda bog'liqdir. Ushbu maqola deyksisning asosiy turlari - shaxsiy, fazoviy, vaqtinchalik, ijtimoiy va nutq deyxislarini tahlil qiladi va deyktik elementlarni ingliz va o'zbek tillariga tarjima qilishda yuzaga keladigan muammolarni ko'rib chiqadi. Adabiy asarlardan tanlab olingan misollar orqali tadqiqot grammatik tuzilish, ma'daniy me'yorlar va pragmatik konventsionaldagi farqlar tarjima strategiyalariga qanday ta'sir qilishini ko'rsatadi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, deyxisni to'g'ri tarjima qilish nafaqat lingvistik malakani, balki chuqur kontekstual va ma'daniy xabardorlikni ham talab qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: deyxis, tarjimashunoslik, ingliz tili grammatikasi, o'zbek tili, pragmatika, kontekst, deyktik iboralar, fazoviy, diskurse deyxis, pragmatik konvensiyalar.

Аннотация: Дейксис – это фундаментальное лингвистическое явление, отражающее взаимосвязь языка и контекста. Дейксис играет решающую роль в переводоведении, поскольку дейктические выражения в значительной степени зависят от говорящего, времени, места и речевой ситуации. В данной статье анализируются основные типы дейксиса – личный, пространственный, временной, социальный и дискурсивный – и рассматриваются проблемы, возникающие при переводе дейктических элементов на английский и узбекский языки. На примере отдельных литературных произведений исследование показывает, как различия в грамматической структуре, культурных нормах и прагматических конвенциях влияют на стратегии перевода. Результаты показывают, что правильный перевод дейксиса требует не только языковой компетенции, но и глубокого контекстуального и культурного понимания.

Ключевые слова: дейксис, переводоведение, английская грамматика, узбекский язык, прагматика, контекст, дейктические выражения, пространственный, дискурсивный дейксис, прагматические конвенции.

Annotation: Deixis is a fundamental linguistic phenomenon that reflects the relationship between language and context. In translation studies, deixis plays a crucial role because deictic expressions are highly dependent on the speaker, time, place, and discourse situation. This article analyzes the main types of deixis – personal, spatial, temporal, social, and discourse deixis – and examines the challenges that arise in translating deictic elements between English and Uzbek. Through selected examples from literary works, the study demonstrates how differences in grammatical structure, cultural norms, and pragmatic conventions influence translation strategies. The findings show that accurate translation of deixis requires not only linguistic competence but also deep contextual and cultural awareness.

Keywords: deixis, translation studies, English grammar, Uzbek language, pragmatics, context, deictic expressions, spatial, discourse deixis, pragmatic conventions.

In recent years, research has drawn attention to the importance of factors such as speech situation, context, general knowledge of the speaker about the object of speech, and language skills in revealing the expressive potential of language units and determining their semantic structure. This is also confirmed by the emergence of new directions and new views in linguistics.

The reality reflected in the language does not always express all the information. The speaker implicitly expresses some information in accordance with his pragmatic purpose. “The need to find the meaningful connection between language units in speech, to refer to the context and through it to restore the information known to the participants of the speech, has created a need to study the phenomenon of deixis”.

Deixis analysis is an analysis in linguistics that aims to determine the meaning of words in speech, such as pronouns, adverbs, and phrases, depending on the context. For example, the speaker’s place, time, and participants, as well as to study various manifestations such as emotional deixis, which plays an important role in understanding the context and rules of politeness in spoken communication. In the research carried out so far, types of deixis such as person, object, sign, quantity, time, space, social, and emotional have been studied.

The word deixis is derived from the Greek language and means indication, that is, it is currently used in linguistics to indicate the function of personal and demonstrative pronouns, tense, and various other grammatical and lexical features. Therefore, the concept of deixis is recognized in many sources as having deep roots in the history of Greek philosophy. In linguistics, there are five

different types of the concept of deixis, which include: time deixis, person deixis, place deixis, social deixis, and discursive deixis.

In linguistics, personal deixis is the most common linguistic category, used to indicate the function of a person. Personal deixis has been studied by a number of scholars around the world to this day. For example, the German linguist Karl Bühler is considered the founder of the linguistic concept of deixis. His theory of the field and his work on communicative phenomena are especially noteworthy. According to early grammatical theories, deixis was described in detail in his work by the Greek linguist Dionysius Thrax and introduced to the West. Later, his student Apollonius Discolus contributed to this work.

In the 20th century, the German scientist, philosopher, and psychologist Karl Bühler introduced the theory of deixis into language and analyzed it in depth. He emphasized the role of communicative context and deictic words in expressing the speaker's point of view. Personal deixis pronouns function as possessive, participial, and complement in a sentence. This helps the speaker and listener to determine who is speaking, who is talking, or what is being discussed. This is very important for understanding the relationships between the individuals involved in communication.

Various researchers have studied the use of deixis in different contexts, such as classroom interactions, literature, and song lyrics. Personal deixis refers to the speaker's and listener's participation in the discourse, combining the speaker's and listener's attitude to the person in the discourse, while third-person pronouns occur without speech or with the help of a narrator.

The deixis field is centered on the individual. The composition of the deixis of the individual is determined by the role he plays in the process of speech communication. The first person is a linguistic expression of reference to the speaker, "showing himself, reminding himself", the second person is a linguistic designation of the listener or addressee, and the third person is a reference to a person who is not a direct participant in the communication. This system, which differs in terms of its contribution to the transfer of communication, is reflected in the groups of pronouns.

One of the main goals is to show the specific features of the expression of personal deixis in scientific texts, to analyze deictic units that are characteristic of oral speech but not used in written scientific speech using examples. The article also analyzes the similarities and differences between existing deictic units in English and Uzbek.

In linguistics, the phenomenon of deixis has been analyzed by many linguists. When dividing deixis into types, personal deixis was initially divided into three types. Later, in research conducted by other linguists, personal deixis is distinguished within deictic units. The philosopher Bertrand Russell, who gave an egocentric theory of expressing personal deixis, defined the words “I”, “this”, “here”, “now” as the main egocentric words, recognizing that their meaning changes in connection with changes in time and space.

Levinson argues that the main focus in personal deixis should be on grammaticalization, based on the idea that when speakers switch, the existing deictic center in the deictic system shifts from one participant to another. He argues that we need to develop an independent pragmatic structure of possible participant roles so that we can see how and to what extent these roles are grammaticalized across languages.

It should be noted that the speaker or agent is different from the source of the utterance, the receiver from the target, and the listeners or observers from the addressee or target, and that sometimes such differences are expressed in a grammatically unclear manner. In personal deictic, a linguistic expression is used to emphasize a specific person who has not yet been linguistically isolated in the context. According to Benveniste, the meaning of the pronoun “I” can only be determined in relation to the performance of a specific speech act, and this speech act is always unique, not repeated. Since each speech act is associated with a separate object, the referent of the pronoun “I” also changes.

In his Pragmatics, Yule mentioned inclusivity and exclusivity as one of the characteristics of personal deixis, in the distinction between saying “Let’s go” and “We went”. Lyons also emphasizes that this idea is necessary, and that this feature is important for some languages. The first and second persons are participants in the dialogue, and the pronouns in the groups “I” and “you” represent “communicative persons”. Third-person pronouns do not have this feature, their referent is “non-communicative persons”, who are not direct participants in the dialogue.

In Uzbek linguistics, we can find the phenomenon of deixis in the scientific research of a number of linguists. For example, S. Safarov analyzed the phenomenon of deixis from a pragmalinguistic point of view in his work “Pragmalinguistics”, A. Shermatov studied the manifestation of deixis in scientific and technical texts, G. Boltakulova studied the expression of temporal deixis in the Uzbek language, and R. Davlatova conducted scientific research on deictic units in the Uzbek language.

When analyzing the phenomenon of personal deixis, it is impossible not to mention personal pronouns. Betty Birner says: "Personal pronouns directly refer to individuals, but through context they indicate who that individual is. Therefore, personal pronouns can be characterized as deictic units that clarify the concept of person through reference".

The units referring to the person cannot be imagined without the speaker - "I". The speaker is central in the communication process. The position of other speech participants is determined in relation to this same speaker, that is, the speaker. "Subordination to the speaker" is considered a necessary and central feature of other personal pronouns.

In literary works, especially fairy tales, myths, epics, novels, trilogy, stories, and poetry, the author is often required to be creative and to select and use words with a rich meaning, and to create a work based on this. However, no matter how well-chosen, clear, and clearly understood the words are, repeating them repeatedly in describing one or another event leads to a certain degree of stylistic monotony, that is, uniformity.

This situation is especially noticeable in the texts of literary works and causes boredom for the reader. Therefore, in order to fully reveal an event to the reader and illuminate its true essence using stylistic methods of language, the writer often has to find synonymous equivalents of sentences that do not seriously harm the narrative of the work and provide a lively and impressive artistic style. In this process, the phenomena of deixis and anaphora are opposed to each other.

Today, personal deixis attracts many linguists. The main reason for this is that in order to fully understand the content of the text and to cognitively analyze the event, a person imagines reality as if it were happening before his own eyes. Events and processes occurring in reality are evaluated based on the person's own "I". A person not only perceives reality, but also describes it to the addressee based on his own discursive thinking.

The main goal of deixis analysis is to eliminate ambiguity in communication, improve the effectiveness of speech, and analyze the use of emotional deixis in texts such as social media discourses. In fact, deixis analysis is an analysis that is important for understanding the meaning of a text in context, using appropriate language in the process of verbal communication, and understanding the rules of politeness.

When analyzing the deictic units used in the poems of Osman Azim, we encounter deictic units that do not correspond to the above types of deixis. We

can call such deixis referring to Allah and the afterlife. In the poet's poetry, references to the Creator, supplication, appeal to Him, and Allah are manifested in a unique way. In the poet's poems, references to the Creator are made using the pronoun you.

In conclusion, in scientific sources on the use of deixis units, there is a classification of deixis based on different approaches. All of the above types of deixis serve to reveal some aspect of it. Also, the deictic units we have analyzed are distinguished from other types of deixis in terms of their referential capabilities.

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